

BUCKLING OF A LAMINATE WITH REALISTIC MULTIPLE DELAMINATIONS AND FIBRE FRACTURE CRACKS USING FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY

This paper presents a finite element study of buckling and postbuckling of sublaminates representative of an impact damaged laminate. Multiple realistic delaminations and fibre fracture cracks are considered under compression to identify the key parameters of impact damage that affect the residual compressive strength of the laminate.

Keywords: Buckling, Delamination, Impact Damage, Finite Element, Compression

INTRODUCTION

Composites are used extensively for their high strength, stiffness and low density, compared to metals. This makes them particularly attractive to the aircraft industry which is using 50% composites by weight on the new Airbus A350. The caveat with composite structures is their susceptibility to damage in the out-of-plane direction, which can cause extensive internal damage even at low impact energies, leaving little or no sign of damage on the surface of the structure [1]. This damage can lead to significant reductions in strength and stiffness of up to 60% compared to undamaged material, [2].

There have been many studies over the past 30 years that have looked at the effect of impact damage loaded in compression using; analytical, [3]-[5], experimental, [6]-[8] and FE techniques, [9]-[11]. While these studies have achieved good correlation between models and experiments and can predict the buckling load to within 10-15% they are unable to capture the local buckling behaviour of the impacted region. Circular sublaminates do not buckle in the same way as real impact damage, so the buckling behaviour of the sublaminates is noticeably different. One possibility that was considered in [10] was that the earlier models did not consider the effect of fibre fracture and matrix cracking in the impact damaged region. An attempt in [10] to model this with a softened region proved unsuccessful and a later study showed that the expected brooming effect of the fibres was unlikely to occur, [12]. Another possibility is the fact that the delaminations modelled in most studies have been simple geometries, namely circular or elliptical, compared to the complex stack of peanut shapes that occur in actual impact damage Fig. 1a and 1b. To the best of the author's knowledge, the only

attempt to model sublaminates buckling with more realistic delaminations is Suemasu, [11].

Figure 1a) 2D C-scan of impact damage, [13] b) 3D C-scan of impact damage, [13] c) Computer generated model of idealised delaminations.

The aim of this work is to model multiple delaminations with realistic delamination shapes Fig. 1c, include fibre fracture cracks and study the effect of lay-up, delamination size and shape and fibre fracture cracks. This work follows on from the study of impact damage in tension, [14] and includes the findings of the micromechanics study of fractured fibres under compression in the modelling of fibre fracture cracks, [12], [15].

MODELLING TECHNIQUE

FE modelling is conducted using ABAQUS 6.8/Standard, a commercially available implicit FE code. The models replicate the standard Boeing CAI test specimen size of 154 mm by 100 mm. The carbon fibre epoxy pre-preg modelled is IM7/8551-7, the properties are; $E_{11} = 165$ GPa, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 8.4$ GPa, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.6$ GPa, $G_{23} = 2.8$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.34$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.5$. Four different laminate lay-ups are modelled, each of which is a, balanced, eight ply, quasi-isotropic (QI) laminate, with a total thickness of 1 mm. The stacking sequences are; $(0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$, $(+45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ)_s$, $(-45^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/0^\circ)_s$ and $(90^\circ/0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ)_s$.

The models are constructed from individual plies that are constructed of C3D20 elements, a 20 node quadratic brick element. The plies have one element through the thickness and between 500 and 2500 elements across the surface of the ply, depending on the complexity of the geometry that is being modelled. The mesh is generated using the hex-dominated, advancing front algorithm within ABAQUS, based on local seeding to enable a much refined mesh where it is required around the damage region and a coarser mesh elsewhere.

The delaminations have different shapes depending on whether they are for the thin film models with a single sublaminates, Fig. 2a or for multiple delaminations Fig. 2b. The thin film delamination were chosen to match those in, [3] and the multiple delaminations with more realistic delamination pattern are taken from [14] and designed to be a closer match to real impact induced delaminations.

Figure 2a) Delamination and crack patterns for single delamination models b) Delamination and crack patterns for multiple delamination models

The delaminations were also modelled in three different sizes 10 mm, 20 mm, and 30 mm to determine the effect of size on buckling load. To construct the delamination, the delamination is drawn onto the top surface of the ply as a sketch, which is then extruded through the ply to create a constant section through the thickness of the ply to allow for uniform meshing of the ply. This process is the same regardless of the shape of the delamination.

The plies are tied together using the tie constraint within ABAQUS, as delamination growth is not considered in this work, where the focus is on the effect of different damage parameters on delamination buckling. The tie constraint could easily be replaced by cohesive surfaces or cohesive elements if delamination growth was required. Surfaces are defined on the ply faces so that all the ply face apart from the delaminated region is included. This means that the plies can be tied together leaving only the delaminated regions unconnected.

The boundary conditions (BC) applied to the models, Fig. 3a, are designed to simulate idealized compression after impact (CAI) conditions with global buckling of the plate prevented and only local buckling of the damage region allowed. The bottom edge is constrained in the loading (y-direction) but free to move in the x-direction to allow for Poisson's effects. The top edge has a compressive displacement applied which equates to 1% applied compressive strain, increasing linearly from 0% initially.

Figure 3 a) Boundary Conditions for the FE models, b) Contact locations for the multiple peanut delamination models.

To enable the delaminations to buckle when the compressive load is applied, an initial pressure force is applied to the surface of the delaminations to cause a local numerical instability in the model, ensuring buckling will occur under compressive load. This is similar to the technique applied in [11], where a force was applied to a point or a line. It was, however, found that the results were unaffected by an applied pressure whereas the results were sensitive to an applied point force.

Contact is applied between all delamination surfaces of the models, as shown in Fig. 3b, these were prescribed master and slave surfaces between each pair of contacting surfaces and the Augmented Lagrange contact algorithm was used to model the contact. A few iterations were required to determine the correct contact parameters to achieve convergence. With fibre fracture cracks introduced into the models, the contact problem becomes much greater; the cracks are modelled as highly elongated elliptical cut outs [14]. This means that contact must be added to these two crack faces as well to prevent interpenetration of the crack surfaces when loaded in compression. The cracks have been modelled as cracks rather than softened regions based on the findings in [12]. These cracks are placed perpendicular to the fibre direction of the ply where they are located. This gives the line pattern shown in Fig. 2a, for the single delamination models and the star pattern for multiple delaminations, Fig. 2b.

THIN FILM MODELS

The main purpose of the thin film models is to act as preliminary or development models, to determine the best modelling and solution techniques for the more complex and realistic multiple delamination models. Consequently problems with meshing, contact, buckling initiation and fibre fracture cracks can be addressed in simpler models before being applied to more complex models.

The models are also much faster to solve taking only 4 to 6 hours on the High Performance Cluster (HPC) at Imperial College London, utilising 1 CPU with 4GB of RAM.

The other purpose of these models is to check the accuracy of the FE models compared with existing analytical solutions such as [3] which are available in the literature and have been frequently cited.

These thin film models have a sublaminate consisting of a single ply, with either an elliptical or circular delamination, in one of three diameters (diameter equates to major axis for the ellipse) 10 mm, 20 mm or 30 mm.

Figure 4 Delamination orientation and position for thin film models

The ellipses have an aspect ratio of 2:1. Four fibre orientations are considered for the different ply lay ups. In the case of the ellipses the major axis is orientated along the fibre direction of the sublaminates, Fig. 4. The findings of these models will be discussed in the results section.

MULTIPLE DELAMINATIONS

Impact damage cannot be successfully modelled using a single delamination, or even with multiple circular delaminations. Thus, these models expand on the fan shape delaminations in [11]. The idea being that more realistic delaminations should mimic the behaviour of real impact damage more closely.

These models have seven delaminations per model, i.e. one at each ply interface; there have been several studies that suggest that delaminations do not occur between plies of the same orientation, although other studies do [16]. Delaminations have been included between all plies in these models for ease of modelling, although no significant difference in results was found for a test case run with and without delamination between plies of the same orientation.

In terms of computational requirements these models are much more demanding requiring runs of 24-30 hours using 4 CPU's and 16GB of RAM. Consequently the number of models that can be run is limited. For this reason the reference case model in this study is considered to be a 30 mm peanut without cracks and a $(0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ lay-up. This is the reference case which other damage models will be compared too and only one parameter will be changed at a time, so for instance for lay-up all models compared will have 30 mm peanuts without cracks and only the lay-up will change.

The parameters that have been investigated in this manner are; delamination shape, delamination size, lay-up, and the fibre fracture cracks idealized in a star pattern, as this was found to be the worst case scenario in [14].

Determining Stiffness Reduction

In order to determine the stiffness reduction from these models the stiffness reduction was quantified using the inverse method in [17]. This method takes the displacement field from the front and back plies of the model outside the delamination zone at different applied strains and uses the information to determine membrane (in-plane) displacements.

The membrane displacements are then matched to the strain field on a simple shell FE model where the damaged region is replaced by a homogenous soft inclusion. The material properties of the soft inclusion namely, Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν are changed using an iterative process called the steepest descent gradient method in order to match the displacements from the detailed FE model and the soft inclusion model. This then gives the reduction in E and ν from which the stiffness reduction is calculated. The average stress and strain in the soft inclusion with converged properties E and ν are finally used to generate a nonlinear stress-strain curve.

RESULTS

This section provides an overview of the result trends for both the thin film and multiple delamination models and gives more detailed explanations and graphs for particular cases.

Thin Film Delamination Results

For the sake of brevity only the results of the circular delaminations with different fibre orientations will be discussed in detail. The results from these models can be seen in Fig. 5, which shows the maximum out-of-plane displacement against applied strain for different sublaminates. It also shows the distribution of out-of-plane displacements in the sublaminate at different applied strains to show how the delaminations develop and the buckling modes change.

Figure 5 Applied compressive strain vs. OOP deflection for circular thin film delaminations.

The results show that there is an increasing sublaminate deflection for all the laminates with the zero degree showing the biggest buckle and the 90 degree the smallest as it has several ripples rather than one large buckle. These results also agreed well with the analytical results using the Rayleigh-Ritz (R-R) model from [3]. The difference between models and R-R is likely to be caused by over prediction of the buckling load by the R-R due to the limited number of terms used. In most cases (except for 90° sublaminates) the buckles involved one mode, which grew in amplitude but narrowed in length as the applied strain increased. In some cases these buckles switched to a second mode at the highest strains, Fig. 5. The elliptical sublaminates exhibited the same behaviour although the buckle was confined to the widest part of the ellipse and the narrow ends tended to show no buckling, or very limited buckling, at higher buckling modes.

Multiple Delamination Results

The multiple delamination models in this paper have been used to consider the effect of four different damage parameters on the residual stiffness of the laminate. These are lay-up, delamination shape, delamination, size, and fibre fracture cracks. The general trends of lay-up and delamination shape will be discussed in the text, and the effect of

delamination size and fibre fracture cracks are demonstrated on graphs and will be discussed in more detail.

All the results have been plotted as the equivalent local average compressive stress, against the equivalent local average compressive strain of the impact damage region. This plot is compared with a plot for the undamaged material which displays linear behaviour. The plots for the impact damaged regions show linear behaviour up to buckling and then nonlinear behaviour after buckling has occurred.

In the case of delamination shape, two different shapes are considered twin ellipse and peanut, Fig 2. The results show that the peanut delaminations buckle at a much lower strain and have a much lower stiffness compared with the twin elliptical models. At 1% applied compressive strain the peanut delamination shows a 65% stiffness reduction compared with the undamaged material, as opposed to a 40% reduction for the twin ellipse model. This is believed to be due to the twin ellipse having a non delaminated core which means that two smaller local buckles have to form, which have higher buckling strain compared with the large single buckle of the peanuts.

The effect of different lay-ups is much less pronounced, with less than 10% difference in the stiffness reduction between the lay-ups, although this is still around a 60% stiffness reduction compared to the undamaged material. The lay-ups that show least reduction seem to have the 0° closer to the mid plane, suggesting that it is the buckling of the major load bearing plies that has some effect on the overall stiffness reduction.

Figure 6 Effect of delamination size on stiffness of impact damage region loaded in compression

The effect of delamination size on the stiffness of the impact region is shown in Fig. 6. As expected, the results show that the buckling of the damage region starts at increasing levels of strain the smaller the diameter of damage. Furthermore, the larger the delaminations the lower the residual stiffness compared with the undamaged material. The cross section views are taken through the mid-plane vertically, so the top delamination is full length of the zero degree sublaminates buckled peanut, and only the mid section for other peanut delaminations are visible in this cut. They also show the sequence of buckling, where the 10 mm only undergoes local sublaminates buckling, the

20 mm model starts to buckle globally within the damage region, and the 30 mm sample shows initial local buckling of sublaminates which is mostly suppressed by the global buckling of the damaged region.

Figure 7 shows the effect of introducing fibre fracture cracks into the impact damage region. The overall stiffness reduction is not significantly influenced, as the reduction at one percent applied compressive strain is 71% with fibre cracks compared with 65% without fibre cracks. The behaviour of the damage region changes, however, as the presence of cracks means that the damage region is degraded even at very low strains and no longer follows the linear behaviour of the undamaged material up to initial buckling.

Figure 7 Effect of fibre fracture cracks on stiffness of impact damage region loaded in compression

The other important difference in behaviour is the change in buckling mode, which has gone from a typical mode two buckle, to a sharper chevron shaped mode one buckle, where the fibre fracture cracks cause the plies to behave like individual plies butted against each other and buckling together rather than a single plate, Fig 8. The fact that

Figure 8 Influence of fibre fracture cracks on buckling behaviour

the fibre fracture cracks are implemented in a star crack pattern, an idealised severe case of fibre fracture, will mean that the influence on the buckling behaviour of the fibre fracture cracks is exaggerated, as cracks of equal orientation appear on to of each other. Nevertheless, it still shows that fibre fracture cracks influence the buckling behaviour, so that fibre fracture cracks need to be included in the models in order to correctly model the behaviour of impact damaged regions under compressive loading.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion the study has led to the development of a an FE model of impact damage loaded in compression which can be used to determine the effects of many different damage parameters, including multiple delaminations with realistic size and shape and idealised fibre fracture cracks. The results have clearly shown the effect on the stiffness reduction of impact damage regions for four different damage parameters; lay-up, delamination shape and size and the presence of fibre fracture cracks.

The effect of delamination shape is the most significant with twin elliptical delaminations reducing the stiffness compared with undamaged material much less than the peanuts. This is believed to be due to the central non-delaminated region in the twin ellipse model, raising the buckling strain and stiffness of the impact damaged region considerably. The lay-up seems to be less significant for the residual stiffness with some small variation between the lay-ups, which seems to be caused by the ability of the zero degree sublaminates to buckle locally. Delamination size has an obvious effect, with larger delamination sizes causing more significant stiffness reductions. This is due to the onset of global buckling of the impact damage region occurring at lower strains for larger delaminations. Fibre fracture cracks only have a small influence on the stiffness in compression unlike in tension. They do however change the buckling behaviour of the laminate considerably and need to be included in a model to replicate the behaviour of impact damage accurately.

There is work still to be done on this study, which includes considering the effects of matrix cracks on ply behaviour, considering the effects of the damage distribution through the thickness of the laminate and finally trying to replicate a real impact and buckling load from coupon tests to validate these models.

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